

THE EFFECT OF MOTIVATION FACTORS ON EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE IN PENANG MANUFACTURING FIRMS, MALAYSIA

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ABSTRACT

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This study evaluated the relationship between motivation factors on employees' performance in manufacturing firms in Penang, Malaysia. A sample size of 222 respondents was taken from 28 electrical manufacturing firms with a 6322 population and 361 samples to examine the relationship. A questionnaire was designed for data collection to measure learning activities on employees' performance in manufacturing firms. A stratified sampling method was used, and the data was analyzed using SmartPls 3.7.8. The study showed that financial rewards and friendly work environment have a significant relationship with employees' performance in manufacturing firms. The result also showed that career development has not significant on employees' performance in manufacturing firms. However, the limitation of this study only covers electrical manufacturing firms. Suggested for future study focus on electronic, plastic, and fabricated manufacturing firms to be more effective in improving manufacturing firms' motivation factors.

KEYWORDS:-Job Motivation, Communication and Work Relationship, Salary and Remuneration, Organizational Effectiveness.

1. Introduction

Motivation is a set of external and internal factors that motivate an employee to carry out tasks related to his job and to devote himself to the maximum in it. In general, it relates to emotional states and attitudes that drive, sustain, and direct behavior within the scope of work. Motivation factors in this study covered financial rewards, career development, and friendly environment for employees’ performance in the workplace. Understanding how motivation works is fundamental in almost every field, but in the workplace, motivation becomes more important because the presence of these factors is positively correlated with other employees such as job performance or benefits earned by firms (Imam& Soo,2018).Motivation is "the work of maintaining a corporate culture and tasks that lead to high performance." For this reason, in the past decade, the way firms work has been studied in-depth, and there have been attempts to create programs to promote it. Interventions in the field of motivation focus a lot on changes in the external circumstances of employees, such as helping them improve their attitudes and thoughts. In this article, we will look in-depth at how motivation works, why it is so important, and what can be done to improve it. The motivation of each employee (regardless of whether he works with others or if he has his own business) depends on many factors that motivate him to make maximum effort in his job. Depending on elements such as personality, personal values, or past experiences each individual and each situation affects to a lesser or greater degree. Different theories are the most important factor in employee motivation; but one of the most accepted classifications is that which deals with matters relating to financial reward, personal satisfaction, flexibility, impact, and social recognition. Motivation is a determining factor in improving job performance because highly motivated employees can perform tasks efficiently and with discipline.

2. Research Objectives and Research Questions

2.1 Research Objectives

1. To evaluate the relationship between financial rewards on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms.
2. To examine the relationship between career development on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms.
3. To identify the relationship between friendly work environment on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms.

2.2 Research Questions of the Study

1. Is there any relationship between financial rewards on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms?
2. Is there any relationship between career developments on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms?
3. Is there any relationship between friendly work environments on employees’ performance in manufacturing firms?

3. Literature Review

3.1 Financial Rewards

Financial rewards are financial rewards given by firms for the performance of a task assigned to them. A previous study stated that there is a significant relationship between financial rewards on employees ’performance. When thinking about why employees work, the first thing that comes to mind is money. The majority of workers have jobs because they need a salary to live, buy food, pay for accommodation and provide other basic products and

services for themselves and their families. Several studies in this regard show that most employees will devote more time and effort to their jobs if they believe that by doing so, they receive greater financial rewards. This type of motivation is known as “extrinsic” because it comes from outside; which provides rewards in the form of money. In any case, increasing the financial rewards or significant benefits derived from employment is one of the easiest and most effective ways to increase employee work motivation in firms (Oravee, Zayum& Kokona,2018;Wairiuko,Nyonje& Omulo,2018). Intrinsic motivation plays a role in allowing employees to do quality work and can be appreciated. However, it is necessary to use monetary rewards as an intrinsic motivator. All employees should receive both forms of reward to maximize their job performance. Efforts to improve the performance of firms are an ongoing effort. It not only involves increasing employee salaries, achieving competitive opportunities, adding value in quality, and raising firm returns whether work productivity or product output. Good quality employees can help raise the performance of firms. Improving performance involves selection and training. Employees can work diligently if they are given more monetary rewards (Sagheb-Esmaeelpour, Abdi,Hosseini & Biglarian,2019;Strenitzerova & Achimsky, 2019). Salaries are a key factor in attracting high-quality employees. Incentive schemes can increase production but they can also affect quality. A performance-based pay scheme is better than motivating employees. Employees will work harder and more effectively through rewards if they feel that they are worthwhile and believe that they have a good chance of earning them. The method of motivation through wages will quickly disappear. Wages will be effective if he feels treated fairly. Non-monetary rewards such as praise, appreciation, and opportunities to achieve and develop performance have a longer-lasting effect than monetary rewards. Employees present their best work if they are directly tied to a mutually agreed-upon objective. Employees will become more motivated when they know clearly about what they expect to achieve and know that they will be rewarded commensurate with their efforts to achieve mutually agreed objectives. All employees need to be evaluated either for themselves or their achievements. Financial rewards are a catalyst to job performance because every employee is motivated by financial returns. The higher the finances received the higher the performance of the work they do (Hindrayani & Muhtar,2019;Terry,2019).

3.2 Career Development

Career development is an important motivation that involves the promotion of the best work performance of employees or seniority. Promotion rewards become a priority for every employee if they have the opportunity to earn it through high work results. A previous study found that there is a significant relationship between career developments on employees ’performance. Career development plays an important role in determining the direction of firms while ensuring management efficiency. Thus, firms need to be efficient in ensuring quality services are provided to all parties (Sitohang,2019;Handayani,2019). This article aims to propose a theoretical framework model of the study to investigate the relationship of career development factors to job performance in firms. Previous studies also found that in general, their study proved that the work performance of an employee can be improved if career development is given the widest opportunity for them to improve their work performance. This study is suitable as a reference and can add to the literature in the field of motivation and human resource management. Career development is an important motivation and employees are the most important assets in the organization and need to be seen strategically. Strategic human resource management through a career development approach is a key approach contributing toward the sustainability of a firm (Suparjo & Sunarsih,2019;Amoi,Ramadhania& Hasan,2019). Therefore, producing balanced and

competitive employees requires a comprehensive career development management system to be able to face future challenges. So, business strengthening career development through human resource management practices requires an element of efficient and effective human capital development. These elements range from the identification of motivational factors, recruitment, human resource development, talent retention, career development, and risk management until retirement. This is very important because career development and firms are the main mission movers as one of the main thrusts towards maximizing firms’ achievement (Voca& Havolli, 2019;Henkel& Endres,2019). This effort can realize the firm's desire to increase the level of productivity and competitiveness of employees. Thus, this effort will produce employees as excellent human capital. Therefore, all parties should have a responsibility in ensuring that employees become competent, knowledgeable, skilled, and competent human capital. In line with that, career development is the main catalyst for career advancement of firms and this proves that firms and human resource departments are very committed to efforts to improve human capital development for employees and subsequently produce high-performing human capital through career development strategies built to improve employee performance. Promotion opportunities and job security guarantees for a long period. Career development is an important factor in contributing to high job performance, better work motivation, and satisfactory work productivity (Karim,2019;Yoon, Kim& Eom,2019).

3.3 Friendly Work Environment

Friendly work environment is the basis for increasing employee motivation free from psychological stress involving work stress, overload, and Relationships with superiors. Past studies have found that there is a significant relationship between friendly work environment on employees’ performance. Supervisors provide a friendly work environment and create good relationships between employees and mutual respect among employees (Pratama, 2018; Putri, Ekowati, Supriyanto& Mukaffi,2019). This atmosphere has a positive impact on the work performance of employees and is a motivation for every employee to work more diligently to achieve personal and firm goals. Entering the world of work has become a part of life, so the balance between work and a healthy lifestyle is very important to ensure that employees in a firm can provide good work performance. Generally, each employee spends about 50 percent of their daily active time at work. It proves the workplace has a direct impact on influencing the physical, mental, economic, and social of employees, in turn affecting their level of health, family, community, and the surrounding society. When employees are motivated and active, the organization also gets good work results. Firms that provide health programs find that when employees feel healthy, they work better, take less sick leave and choose to work with the firm longer (Magito,2018;Andi,Prayogi& Yani,2019). A healthy workplace is a workplace that constantly creates and improves the social and physical environment that allows employees to support each other in carrying out tasks and cultivating capabilities to the maximum level. A friendly work environment forms a workplace that is considered good and healthy if it has characteristics, including a clean and safe physical environment, basic needs of employees are provided, mutually supportive relationships, strong, integrated and do not exploit employees, promotes a healthy lifestyle, facilities to various types experience, interaction, and communication as well as high rates of employee engagement (Kristanti& Pangastuti,2019;Aulia,Sucipto & Gunawan,2019). A healthy friendly work environment is very important to ensure that an employee's career can be successful and grow as well as to ensure that their welfare and health are protected and work performance is high. Therefore, firms should be concerned about a friendly work environment that involves the mental and physical health status of employees by providing a

healthy, prosperous and safe work environment and environment. With that concern, employees will be willing to do more work than what is entrusted to them by including their added value for the good of a firm. The role of supervisors who build a friendly work environment is the most important motivation in producing the best work performance among employees to continue to work and strive so that their best achievements can be achieved (Antara,2018;Gamal, Taneo& Halim,2018).

3.4 Employees’ Performance

Employees' performance refers to the quality and productivity of performance in handling their daily tasks given by the organization. To perform a task, employees need a good level of thinking, job knowledge, skills, capability, and desire to improve their work performance to be more professional in performing their daily responsibilities (Martono & Putri, 2018; Sendawula, Nakyejwe Kimuli,Bananuka& Najjemba Muganga,2018;). Recognition of employees creates a positive, productive, and innovative organizational climate in addition to looking at the factors of caring for employee welfare, which is also recognized to affect the employee atmosphere in an organization which is based on various forms of welfare packages created by the organization in producing excellent levels of work performance. The recognition is given, actually encourages more action, and stimulates an employee's thinking to believe that they have the potential and ability to continue to contribute to the progress and success of their organization. Employees' performance through recognition of employees is a form of credit for the quality of work shown by the employees because quality employees are the main assets of an organization (Beltran-Martin & Bou-Llusar, 2018).The quality of work is how a job is executed, and the output from it is the success of meeting the required expectations. If we look at the definition of quality itself is defined as a degree of excellence that is usually high or quality. The quality of work is essential in the management of an organization because, without it, the organization's function, independence, and sustainability can be disrupted (Wang& Guan,2018). Thus, having quality employees at all levels of employment in each department is hope because quality employees translate to the organization's success in producing first-class human resources, which becomes a valuable asset for organizational excellence in the long run. Every employee feels that their organization pays attention to the importance of giving recognition to their ability to handle their daily tasks because it will directly create a new value for employees in the organization is the value to 'give more' and 'not count' while serving the organization (Lakshmi, Narahari& Koneru,2018). When employees can produce output as expected, employees' performance is in a state of availability in handling whatever task is directed. Excellent employee performance positively impacts the organization's performance to continue to grow in maximizing profits and wealth (Bernanthos,2018; Soelton,2018).

4. Conceptual Framework

4.1 Independent Variables

- Financial Rewards
- Career Development
- Friendly Work Environment

4.2 Dependent Variable

- Employees’ performance in Manufacturing Firms

4.3 Hypothesis Development

H1. There is significant relationship between financial rewards on employees' performance in manufacturing firms.

H2. There is significant relationship between career development on employees' performance in manufacturing firms.

H3. There is significant relationship between friendly work environment on employees' performance in manufacturing firms.

5. Data Analysis

5.1 Participants

The data was collected from 28 electrical manufacturing firms, 6822 employees, 361 questionnaires were distributed, and 222 questionnaires were analyzed among the employees (Krejcie and Morgan schedule, 1970). The respondents were selected using the stratified sampling technique.

5.2 Measurement Scale

Questionnaires are designed in Linkert Scale (Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, and Strongly Agree).

5.3 Data Analysis

The data obtained were studied using SmartPLS version 3.7.8 to discuss the findings obtained. Statistical scholars highly recommend SmartPLS in producing an accurate analysis of each variable's cause and effect relationship. SmartPLS is also a sizeable multivariate analysis technique in social and psychological research. In addition, SmartPLS can analyze measurement model evaluation and structural model evaluation.

Table 1 shows the Loading, Composite Reliability (CR), Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for each construct studied; and the lowest value is **0.5020**, and the highest value

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is **0.5664**. These values are more significant than 0.5 (> 0.5), confirming that the study construct can explain the mean change of variance within the items (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Gefen & Straub, 2005; Henseler, Ringle & Sinkovics, 2009).

**Table 1
Loading, CR & AVE Results**

	<i>Loading</i>	<i>CR</i>	<i>AVE</i>
Financial rewards		0.8097	0.5163
FR1	0.7171		
FR2	0.6463		
FR4	0.7453		
FR5	0.7602		
Career Development		0.8857	0.5638
CD1	0.7806		
CD2	0.7517		
CD3	0.7523		
CD4	0.7552		
CD5	0.7149		
CD6	0.7489		
Friendly Work Environment		0.8868	0.5664
FW1	0.7310		
FW2	0.7442		
FW3	0.7590		
FW4	0.7578		
FW5	0.7526		
FW6	0.7645		
Employees’ Performance		0.8581	0.5020
EP1	0.7389		
EP2	0.7179		
EP3	0.7070		

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EP5	0.6955
EP7	0.6987
EP8	0.6922

Figure 1: Structural Model Direct Effects

The discriminate validity test was measured through two methods, namely the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) criterion test and cross-loading (Henseler et al., 2009). Table 2 below shows the output from the HTMT analysis. The results can be calculated easily using the formula as in (Henseler, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2015).

**Table 2
Discriminant Validity**

Constructs	CD	EP	FR
FW			
CD	0.7508		
EP	0.6114	0.7085	
FR	0.6878	0.6210	0.7186
FW	0.6002	0.7292	0.5407
0.7526			

Note: Values in Bold face are the square root values of average variance extracted

5.4 Assessment of Structural Model

The findings for testing this direct effect model using SmartPLS software package version 3.7.8 through the structural equation model. This measurement aims to test the direct effect model and the effective model of the mediated variable. Therefore, empirical evidence has been used to construct a direct effect model, as shown in Figure 3.

Table 3
Summary of Hypotheses

<i>Relationship</i>	<i>Summary of Hypotheses</i>				
	beta	Std Error	T-Value	P-Value	Decision
FR->EP	0.2559	0.0669	3.8193	0.0000	Significant
CD->EP	0.1291	0.0740	1.7101	0.0873	Not-Significant
FW->EP	0.5129	0.0645	7.9865	0.0000	Significant

6. Result

6.1 Financial Rewards

The results obtained showed that financial rewards variable have significantly affects employees’ performance in manufacturing firms ($\beta = 0.2559$; $t = 3.8193$; $p = 0.0000$). H1 Accepted. The results also showed that financial rewards contributed 25.5% ($R^2 = 0.255$) to employees’ performance in manufacturing firms.

6.2 Career Development

The results obtained showed that career development variable have not-significantly affects employees’ performance in manufacturing firms ($\beta = 0.0740$; $t = 1.7101$; $p = 0.0873$). H2 Rejected. The results also showed that career development contributed 12.6% ($R^2 = 0.126$) to employees’ performance in manufacturing firms.

6.3 Friendly Work Environment

The results obtained showed that friendly work environment variable have significantly affects employees’ performance in manufacturing firms ($\beta = 0.5129$; $t = 7.9865$; $p = 0.0000$). H3 Accepted. The results also showed that friendly work environment contributed 51.5% ($R^2 = 0.515$) to employees’ performance in manufacturing firms.

7. Conclusion

The result found that there is a significant relationship between financial rewards on employees’ performance. Employee financial rewards can be highly effective in motivating and encouraging productivity on the job and in recognizing when team members go beyond their normal job duties to contribute to their firms. From additional allowances to employee bonuses, financial incentives give firms a way to compensate their teams for succeeding and

achieving goals. If employees are supporting the development of an incentive program for their firms, consider financial incentives types can integrate into an effective reward system for their team. Financial incentives are a type of employee incentive that manufacturing firms provide to encourage performance and productivity and to recognize achievements. Firms use financial incentives to motivate teams and employees to exceed expectations or otherwise take part in tasks or activities that employees may not normally perform. Additionally, financial incentives are effective rewards for recognizing when employees perform beyond their normal work duties. Firms may implement a range of financial incentives, depending on the work environment and type of business. Financial incentives can be an extremely beneficial motivator in the workplace. Companies that provide some type of monetary reward for exceptional work performance or team recognition are more likely to foster positive work environments, build supportive relationships and encourage higher quality outputs. Consider several more reasons financial incentives are important in the workplace, boost employee satisfaction, recognized individual performance, encourage collaborative teamwork, and motivate employees to achieve manufacturing firms’ objectives.

The result showed that there is a not-significant relationship between career developments on employees’ performance. The result found that career development did not support the performance of employees in manufacturing firms. Therefore, manufacturing firms must be stressed that current information about the firms and future trends helped employees create more realistic career development goals. Focus on employees' interests and skill development that contributed to learning opportunities. Opportunities for promotion and/or lateral moves contribute to the employee's career satisfaction. A greater sense of responsibility for managing one's career contributes to self-confidence. Career planning for development clarifies the match between manufacturing firms and individual employee goals. It is cost-effective to use your own employees’ talent to provide career development opportunities within their department. Career development increases employee motivation and productivity. Attention to career development helped manufacturing firms attract top employees and retain valued employees. Supporting career development and growth of employees is mandated by the Philosophy of Human Resources Management to ensure that employees' performance is maintained. Building skills or making employees ready to directly jump into the corporate firms is not a task of one day. One needs to understand their abilities, their key strengths and weaknesses, which helps them to know what area needs improvement and what needs practice, resulting in personal growth as well as professional growth. The importance of career development lies in the fact that a clear understanding of an individual’s professional abilities and strengths to constantly push them forward in career growth is imperative to achieve success. Moreover, the professional growth of employees leads to a progressive manufacturing firm.

The result found that there is a significant relationship between friendly work environments on employees’ performance. Taking care of a friendly workplace environment improved productivity, helped to retain talent, and most important of all: it is good for the manufacturing firms' overall mental health. No job is perfect, not even those which have an amazing office, a high salary, or the tasks are completely vocational. However, whether these conditions exist or, more importantly, when they do not, there is one thing that can save countless situations: taking care of a friendly workplace environment. A friendly workplace environment with a working atmosphere, to put it another way- is what employees cannot see and cannot touch, but makes employees enjoy going to work, feel comfortable entering the

office, do not mind giving a little of employees’ time to work, or recommend people around employees to apply for a job in manufacturing firms. It is obvious that, in extreme situations, taking care of the work climate is not an all-powerful remedy against serious problems that a firm may have. However, when things are not so extreme, a positive friendly workplace environment is what tips the balance in favor of a firm to consider that it has adequate conditions to provide sufficient psychological well-being for people. On the contrary, when the friendly workplace environment is bad, stress and de motivation is produced, relationships are tenser and less fruitful, and those who have the opportunity to leave the firm do so as soon as they can. Based on the result stated that several factors should be taken into account when creating a positive friendly workplace environment. The working environment that is established in a firm depends on the people who make it up, the tasks they have to perform, what the workspace is like the leadership style, and other external factors. However, manufacturing firms highlighted some factors that can foster a good friendly working environment in any type of company, good work firms, healthy leadership, a high level of team cohesion, physical atmosphere and ergonomics, physical security, and psychological security.

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